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Institutional Safeguarding Policies For Minors’ Protection In Private Secondary Schools In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

The research examined the institutional safeguarding policies for minors’ protection in private secondary schools in Rivers State. Two research questions and two null hypotheses were raised to guide the study. The descriptive research design method was adopted. The population of this study consisted of 20 Catholic Secondary Schools situated in urban and rural areas of Rivers State, two hundred and eighty (280) academic staff of twenty Catholic secondary schools in Rivers State served as the sample size. The sampling technique was the census technique. The instrument for data collection was a self-constructed questionnaire by the researcher titled: Institutional Safeguarding Policies for Minors’ Protection Questionnaire (ISPMPQ). The reliability coefficient index of 0.79 was determined using Cronbach Alpha Statistics. 280 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the respondents. After which 250 copies were retrieved resulting in a 91% rate. Mean and standard deviation were used in answering the research questions. The null hypotheses were dependent on z-calculated value. The null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Based on the comprehensive findings of the study, along with the in-depth discussions surrounding them and their profound educational implications, it is deduced that the appropriate implementation of institutional safeguarding policies among private schools in Rivers State carries significant importance. It is recommended that All stakeholders in school administration, including principals, teachers, non-teaching personnel, students, parents, as well as other public-spirited individuals and groups, should work together to ensure that institutional safeguarding policies for the protection of minors are effectively implemented and adhered to in every educational institution. This collective effort is essential for creating a safe and secure environment where the well-being of all students is prioritized.

Keywords: institutional safeguarding, policies, minors, protection, private secondary schools

INTRODUCTION

Safeguarding involves taking action to promote the well-being of minors and shield them from harm. It also encompasses protecting minors from abuse and mistreatment and preventing harm to their health or development. Safeguarding is the proactive measures an institution or organization takes to prevent harm, while minor protection involves the response to such harm. In schools, safeguarding involves ensuring that they are run in a manner that actively prevents harm, harassment, bullying, abuse, and neglect, and being prepared to respond appropriately in cases of abuse and neglect. Within

the education sector, teachers and other school staff play a crucial role in ensuring the safety and protection of students. Educational institutions have a vital role in shielding minors from abuse as they have regular contact with them, enabling them to identify signs of abuse and neglect. Schools should also ensure that staff can recognize abuse and are confident in responding to concerns such as allegations and harassment. OXFAM International (2020) outlines three primary areas of safeguarding: prevention, which involves training, communication, and information to avert harm and abuse, reviewing staff screening processes, conducting risk assessments, and evaluating staff capacity to fulfill their duties; support and care, which involves providing resources to support victims of sexual harassment, abuse, and violence, as well as ensuring that staff have access to professional training and real-life experience; and strengthening and harmonizing current policies and procedures, ensuring they are clear and accessible to all, to cultivate an environment where information is shared and people are accountable for their actions.

Safeguarding involves protecting children and adults at risk from harm, abuse, and neglect. It aims to ensure that children receive safe and effective care and have the best outcomes. The history of safeguarding can be traced back to 1889 with the Children Charter and the Prevention of Cruelty to and Protection of Children Act. Today, safeguarding issues include bullying, radicalization, sexual exploitation, grooming, allegations against staff, incidents of self-harm, and forced marriage. Schools play a crucial role in creating a safe environment for children and young people by ensuring that their staff and volunteers do not pose a risk to minors and are trained to respond to concerns. Additionally, schools must teach minors about how to stay safe and to maintain an environment where they feel confident to approach any member of staff if they have a worry or problem. Implementing safe recruitment procedures, staff screening, and codes of conduct, as well as providing continuous training, can help safeguard minors in educational settings.

The responsibility of ensuring the safety of students in schools falls on all individuals who work in an educational setting. Staff members are entrusted with the duty of safeguarding the well-being of the children under their care. This responsibility extends to proprietors, principals, heads of departments, vice-principals, Designated Safeguarding Officers (DSOs), teachers, teaching assistants, dining staff, and matrons, as well as anyone else who spends time with minors. Identifying signs of abuse is a challenging task, and it is not the responsibility of any single individual to determine whether abuse has occurred. However, everyone must report any concerns to the appropriate authorities so that necessary actions can be taken. All members of the institution must remain vigilant for potential indicators of abuse. Safeguarding policies can be likened to the internal regulations that an institution establishes for itself. The primary goal of safeguarding policies in schools is to outline the procedures for protecting minors and reporting any concerns about their welfare to the relevant authorities. Safeguarding policies, such as the Online Safety Policy, Health and Safety Policy, Whistleblowing Policy, Behavior Policy, Anti-Bullying and Harassment Policy, and others, are the internal regulations of the institution that clearly define what measures are in place to keep minors safe. These policies aid in the practical protection of at-risk minors by defining abuse and educating individuals on the steps to take in cases of abuse (Safeguarding Policy/Safe and Sound, 2020).

Safeguarding policies within institutions must cover the maintenance of safe premises and equipment, both inside and outside the school, for them to be considered complete. It is crucial for all staff and volunteers working in these institutions to understand their responsibilities (What should a safeguarding policy include? (2019)). Effective communication standards are of utmost importance in dealing with safeguarding issues, ensuring matters are handled efficiently and effectively to promote accountability and good institutional governance (National Catholic Safeguarding Commission, 2012). The practice of institutional safeguarding faces various challenges, such as corruption, institutional hierarchy, engaging the entire institution, rather than only a few individuals, and issues with child protection being perceived as additional bureaucracy, as well as cultural taboos and people feeling insulted, and so on. In the 21st century, safeguarding policies should be considered essential documents for schools because people are generally more aware of their rights and have a good understanding of what constitutes abuse. Institutional safeguarding policies and their associated procedures alone do not protect minors from abuse; rather, it is their effective articulation and implementation that provides minors with protection. The protection of minors at risk can be achieved

through well-articulated and implemented safeguarding policies within an institution or organization. Institutional safeguarding policies will help to protect minors at risk effectively in practice.

Statement of the Problem

The absence of functional institutional safeguarding policies for minors' protection in private secondary schools in Rivers State poses a significant threat to the future of education in the region. Even when these policies are developed, their implementation is often inadequate. The lack of proper implementation is likely to undermine the effectiveness of these safeguarding policies. A key contributing factor is the insufficient skills of educational administrators in implementing these policies. Without comprehensive training for staff, volunteers, and students on safeguarding issues, the effective protection of minors within private secondary schools seems unlikely. This raises concerns about the availability and effectiveness of safeguarding policies in these schools and the potential challenges faced during their implementation. Additionally, it's essential to assess the compliance level of private secondary schools about institutional safeguarding policies for minors' protection. Understanding these aspects will be crucial for developing strategies to enhance institutional safeguarding policies for minors' protection in Rivers State's private secondary schools.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The study aims to investigate institutional safeguarding policies for minors' protection in private secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives of the study are:

1. To ascertain the availability of safeguarding policies for minors' protection in private secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. To identify the strategies for improving institutional safeguarding policies for minors' protection in private secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

1. What are the institutional safeguarding policies for minors' protection availability in private secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. What are the strategies in place for improving institutional safeguarding policies for Minors' protection in private secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female respondents on the availability of institutional safeguarding policies for minors' protection in private Secondary Schools in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female respondents on the strategies for improving institutional safeguarding policies for minors' protection in private Secondary schools in Rivers State.

Significance of the Study

The study aims to raise awareness about the necessity of having operational safeguarding policies in all private secondary schools. It seeks to ensure that staff, volunteers, parents, and students are well-informed about the policies and adhere to best practices. The research will also help school administrators evaluate the extent to which private secondary schools comply with safeguarding standards. Furthermore, the findings will offer valuable insights for principals, emphasizing the importance of continuous training for staff, volunteers, and students to stay updated on safeguarding issues. Additionally, it highlights the importance of having Designated Safeguarding Officers (DSOs) who are trained to handle reported cases of abuse and maintain accurate records. Ultimately, the research aims to underscore the necessity for private secondary schools in Rivers State to appoint central designated safeguarding officers who can oversee safeguarding issues across all schools in the state.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Institutional Safeguarding

Child abuse has been present throughout human history, but only recently has it been recognized as a distinct issue that children have the right to be protected from. This perspective is already being challenged, and it was instances of cruelty that initially brought public attention to the problem. The

first local Societies for the Prevention of Cruelty to Children were established in Liverpool in 1883 and in London in 1884, eventually becoming the National Society for the Prevention of Cruelty to Children. In 1889, the Children's Charter was passed, allowing state intervention in parent-child relationships for the first time. It was amended in 1894 to allow children to testify in court, to recognize mental cruelty, and to criminalize the denial of medical treatment to a sick child. The Children Act of 1948 led to the establishment of a children's committee and a children's officer in each local authority, following the creation of the Parliamentary Care of children committee in 1945 after the tragic death of 13-year-old Dennis O'Neil at the hands of his foster parents. Furthermore, in 1989, the Children Act granted every child the right to protection from abuse and exploitation and the right to inquiries to safeguard their welfare, coming into effect in England and Wales in 1991. The Protection of Children Act of 1999 was also passed to prevent individuals with a history of child exploitation from working with children. The well-being of minors is crucial to the future of our society, as we are aware that childhood abuse and neglect can have long-lasting effects into adulthood. The safety and welfare of minors have been a growing public concern for quite some time. Several inquiries into the tragic deaths of minors at the hands of their parents, caregivers, and professionals have highlighted shortcomings in efforts to protect minors and promote their welfare (Safeguarding Children, 2002). Avert (2019) defines safeguarding as taking all reasonable steps to prevent harm, particularly sexual exploitation, abuse, and harassment, from occurring; protecting people, especially vulnerable adults and children, from such harm; and responding appropriately when harm does occur. In an organization or institution, safeguarding refers to the safety and welfare of the minors who benefit from their services. Policies are courses of action, guiding principles, or rules used to direct decisions and achieve desired outcomes. They can be seen as the internal laws an organization or institution establishes for itself. Safeguarding policies are documents that outline how staff and others should behave around children, providing a clear roadmap for preventing and responding to evidence of abuse against children.

Online Safety Policy: This concerns the safe and responsible use of technology, often referred to as internet safety or e-safety. It encompasses the use of the internet and other electronic communication methods, as well as electronic security measures to protect minors from illegal, inappropriate, or harmful materials and contacts. It addresses personal online behavior that may cause harm. This policy aims to educate and safeguard students and staff in their use of technology. According to Safeguarding Essentials (2015) and the National Society for the Prevention of Cruelty to Children (2020), every institution responsible for minors should have an online safety policy statement that outlines their commitment to keeping minors safe while using the internet..

Health and Safe Policy: The school's policy aims to establish a safe, secure, and healthy environment for both staff and students. All members of the school community are encouraged to be vigilant and aware of potential risks, while also feeling confident and comfortable in their surroundings. The school serves as a workplace for many individuals and welcomes others. As a service provider, the school has a responsibility to create a safe teaching and learning environment where students and staff can collaborate with confidence, while also considering those who may be impacted by its activities (ROSPA, 2019 & Stoke Primary School, 2019).

Whistleblowing Policy: This policy is designed to facilitate the detection of fraud and misconduct, and to protect students and staff. Every functional school should have a whistleblower policy that protects staff members who report colleagues they believe are doing something wrong or illegal, or are neglecting their duties. This policy plays a key role in safeguarding children and also exists to help individuals raise concerns over any wrongdoing within the school relating to unlawful conduct, financial malpractice, dangers to the public or the environment, and more, in order to prevent risk or harm to the organization. It is designed to be implemented without fear of victimization, subsequent discrimination, disadvantage, or dismissal. According to Hockley (2018), a whistleblowing policy is essential for all schools.

Behaviour Policy: The Behavior Policy outlines how all members of the school can collaborate in a supportive manner. The policy aims to promote an environment where everyone feels happy, safe, and secure, and to foster good relationships among staff in order to work together for the common goal of helping students learn effectively and considerately. The behavior policy also states how the school

will help students develop in a safe and secure environment and become positive, responsible, and increasingly independent members of the school community. The policies aim to promote good behavior rather than simply deter anti-social behavior (Priory Woods Schools & Art College, 2019). The goal of the behavior policy in any school is for every member of the school community to feel valued, respected, and to ensure that everyone is treated fairly and well. It provides an ethos and environment in which everyone feels safe and which enables effective learning. It also teaches children appropriate behavior for different situations. The policy outlines how children with challenging behavior will be supported and aims to raise awareness among children of the need to recognize and manage their emotions and reactions (Clavering Primary School, 2019).

Anti- Bullying and Harassment Policy: This policy outlines the institution's commitment to providing a secure, safe, and respectful school environment for all students and staff. It explains procedures and practices aimed at reducing and eliminating bullying and harassment, as well as the processes to deal with incidents of such behavior, including cyberbullying. This policy aims to prevent and address any behavior considered bullying or harassment. - State Government of Victoria, Australia (2019).

Prevention of Sexual Exploitation and Abuse Policy: The Policy as the name suggest is designed in schools to protect vulnerable individuals from sexual exploitation and abuse by the institution. In the school setting the inherent imbalance of power that exist requires the implementation of necessary safeguarding policy to ensure that the power dynamics is not used to abuse or exploit the students in the school, Management Science for Health (2020).

Strategies for Improving Safeguarding

The term "strategy" is defined by the Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary as "a plan of action designed to achieve a long-term or overall aim." Based on this definition, the following plan of action is suggested to improve institutional safeguarding in Catholic secondary schools in Rivers State: implementation of a Code of Conduct, Police vetting or Clearance, staff screening, establishment of Grievance and Allegation procedures, defining Boundaries, and ensuring Confidentiality and proper Record Keeping. The Child Act of 1989 & 2005 places a duty on organizations to safeguard and promote the well-being of minors, including ensuring that all adults working with or on behalf of children in these organizations are competent, confident, and safe to do so.

Code of Conduct: The United Nations (2010) defines a code of conduct as a "preventive tool." It is a demonstration of one's commitment to self-regulate and maintain proper standards. A code of conduct helps all staff understand their professional boundaries when working with children, establishes acceptable behavior, and needs to be deeply integrated into the overall culture of the organization. This ensures that the outlined standards of behavior towards children become the norms within the institution. In schools, the requirement for a code of conduct becomes mandatory following the new safeguarding guide "Keeping Children Safe in Education" (2014).

Police Vetting or Clearance: This process is conducted to determine whether an applicant has a criminal record. The document serves as a guarantee and involves searching for any prior convictions or jail time, checking credit references, verifying professional licenses and certifications, and tracking employment history.

Staff Screening: This refers to tests given to employees before they are allowed to work for an institution, to ensure they can be trusted and have the right personality for the job. It includes references and credit checks, background checks, and physical/drug testing (WiseGeek, 2020). Staff screening has several goals: to confirm that an employee is qualified for the position, to identify any potential safety risks, and to evaluate personality traits that may be beneficial or problematic for the institution. Staff screening is specifically designed to deter potential abusers from applying to work in institutions that work with children.

Grievance and Allegation Procedure: Officially, a grievance is a complaint about something considered unfair or wrong. Grievance procedures are used to address employee grievances, either formally or informally. An allegation is an accusation, which may be true or false. It is a formal claim against someone, and it remains unproven until it is determined to be true or false. It is important to maintain confidentiality while an allegation is being investigated to protect the parties involved and to

manage any related disciplinary processes. This is done to safeguard children and facilitate inquiries. (Cornwall & Isles of Scilly - Safeguarding Children Partnership Procedures Manual, 2020).

Boundaries: Boundaries are the limits that define one person as separate from others. They provide a clear sense of self and empower people to promote and preserve personal integrity. Boundaries may be physical, mental, or behavioral, and also involve language (Ali, 2020).

Theoretical Review

The Planning Theory

Fainstein (2000) states that the planning theory is known for its top-down and consensus-seeking approaches. Stiftel (2000) argues that the planning theory is the driving force behind policy implementation. This means that the planning theory is the origin from which all planning for public policy processes, leading to implementation, originates. In this context, the planning theory for public policy implementation encompasses the discussions and practices of planners as they carry out their planning responsibilities for an organizational entity or function (Watson, 2003). Ferreira, Silva, Pereira, Braga, Moracs, & Araujo (2009) characterized the planning theory as a collaborative and process-oriented theory, involving the participation of multiple actors over an extended period. Therefore, for this study, the planning theory suggests the integration, consensus-seeking, and project-based approaches to pursue safeguarding policy processes involving the implementation of protection measures for minors in Catholic secondary schools. This theory encompasses three dimensions: the top-down approach, the bottom-up approach, and the hybrid approach.

Top-Down Implementation Approach

According to Barret (2004), the top-down implementation approach focuses on the ability of decision-makers to clearly establish public policy objectives and control the implementation stage. Hill and Hupe (2009) argue that the top-down approach prescribes public policy as an input and public policy implementation as output. Therefore, the top-down implementation approach implies that efficient bureaucratic procedures should be in place to ensure the accurate execution of public policies. This requires public institutions to have adequate resources, established implementation systems, clear responsibilities, and hierarchical control to supervise implementers' actions (Pulz & Treib, 2010).

Bottom-Up Implementation Approach

Hill and Hupe (2009) argued that when implementing public policies, it's important to identify networks of actors from all agencies working together. According to Pulz and Treib (2010), in this approach, the people carrying out the implementation have a lot of freedom, which makes the process very political. As a result, policies are significantly influenced during the implementation phase.

Hybrid Implementation Approach

Based on the Barret (2004) study, the hybrid implementation approach aims to bridge the gap between the top-down and bottom-up approaches by integrating elements from both. Pulz and Treib (2010) also suggested that translating public policy objectives into actions relies on the interaction of various stakeholders with distinct interests and strategies, emphasizing the significance of coordination and collaboration in policy processes. This suggests that the hybrid policy implementation approach encompasses both centralized steering, characteristic of a top-down approach, and local autonomy, characteristic of a bottom-up approach. As a result, a framework for harmonized implementation is established to reconcile the preferences of policymakers (often aligned with a top-down approach) and implementers (advocates of a bottom-up approach) (Chand, 2011).

Additional Implementation Approaches

Policy is a dynamic process (Hill & Hupe, 2002). This implies that the evolution of growth and concept development on policy and its surrogate processes, like implementation, is inevitable. Barrett (2004:259) argued that social scientists have contributed significantly to facilitating the understanding of the implementation process by explaining the gaps in the above-mentioned approaches (i.e., the top-down, the bottom-up, and hybrid approaches). Consequently, other additional implementation approaches evolve from studies of policy implementation.

METHODOLOGY

The research design that was adopted for this study was a descriptive survey. Descriptive survey design deals with gathering, generating and describing data the way they are without manipulating the independent variable. The population of this study consisted of 20 Catholic Secondary Schools situated in urban and rural areas of Rivers State. Specifically, a total number of two hundred and eighty (280) academic staff (i.e. 20 principals and 260 teachers). The sample size of the study comprised all the two hundred and eighty (280) academic staff of twenty Catholic secondary schools in Rivers State. The sampling technique was census technique. The instrument for data collection was a self-constructed questionnaire by the researcher titled: Institutional Safeguarding Policies for Minors' Protection Questionnaire (ISPMPQ). To ensure the face and content validity of the instrument for the study, copies of the instrument were given to experts in the departments of Educational Psychology Measurement and Evaluation, in the Faculty of Education, University of Port Harcourt. To determine the reliability of the instrument, the test-retest method was used to obtain the reliability of the instrument. Copies of the instrument were administered by the researcher with the help of two trained research assistants, who were given some orientation to enable them to get familiar with the methods for administering the instrument correctly. As part of data collection efforts, 280 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the respondents. After which 250 copies were retrieved resulting in a 91% rate. Mean and standard deviation were used in answering the research questions. The null hypotheses were dependent on z- calculated value. The null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question One: *What are the institutional safeguarding policies for minors' protection availability in private secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 4.1: Mean scores and standard deviation of male and female teachers on the institutional safeguarding policies for minors' protection availability in private secondary schools in Rivers State.

SN	Items	Respondents				Mean Set X ₁ X ₂	Decision
		Male 108		Female 147			
		X ₁	SD ₁	X ₂	SD ₂		
1	The school has safeguarding policy (ies)	3.18	0.72	3.29	0.72	3.23	Accept
2	The policy(ies) is specific to your school	2.91	0.76	2.96	0.84	2.93	Accept
3	The safeguarding policy (ies) is approved and signed off by the principal and director of Diocesan Education Board	2.89	0.81	2.82	0.93	2.85	Accept
4	The copy is available on your school intranet and internet sites	2.42	0.89	2.45	0.94	2.43	Reject
5	The safeguarding policy (ies) is visible and accessible in the school	2.69	0.86	2.65	0.94	2.67	Accept
6	The school safeguarding policy (ies) is displayed in your school	2.50	0.84	2.60	1.76	2.55	Accept
7	The safeguarding policy (ies) is reviewed every three years when changes occur in the school or legislative.	2.48	0.90	2.22	0.84	2.35	Reject
Average Mean/Standard Deviation		2.72	0.82	2.71	0.99	2.71	Accept

Data on Table 4.1: presents the mean scores and standard deviation of male and female teachers. The average mean scores were 2.72 for the male teachers and 2.71 for the female teachers. Both average mean were above the criterion mean of 2.5 and this implies that both male and female teachers agreed on the institutional safeguarding policies for minors' protection availability in private secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Question two: What are the strategies in place for improving institutional safeguarding policies for Minors' protection in private secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 4.1 :Mean scores and standard deviation of male and female teachers on the strategies in place for improving institutional safeguarding policies for Minors' protection in private secondary schools in Rivers State.

SN	Items	Respondents				Mean Set X ₁ X ₂	Decision
		Male 108		Female 147			
		X ₁	SD ₁	X ₂	SD ₂		
8	The schools have one or two staff who oversees the implementation of the safeguarding policies.	2.85	0.86	2.71	0.81	2.78	Accept
9	School carry out annual self-audit for safeguarding practices	2.54	0.80	2.23	0.87	2.38	Reject
10	New staff receive a copy of the safeguarding policy (ies) and a code of conduct, at the time of issuing an employment contract	2.66	0.86	2.68	0.85	2.67	Accept
11	Staff read, sign and return copies of the policy (ies) which shows that they are aware of and agree to act in accordance with the policy and signed copies filed in staff personal file	2.53	0.88	2.43	0.86	2.48	Reject
12	Staff/ students who report child safeguarding concerns or are accused of abuse receive appropriate care, support and protection in dealing with all aspect of the case	2.80	0.75	2.60	0.83	2.7	Accept
13	The school have a regular system of reporting to key management forums, including the diocesan education director, to track progress and performance on safeguarding issues	2.76	0.83	2.63	0.90	2.69	Accept
Average Mean/Standard Deviation		2.69	0.83	2.54	0.85	2.61	Accept

Data on Table 4.1 presents the mean scores and standard deviation of male and female teachers. The average mean scores were 2.69 for the male teachers and 2.54 for the female teachers. Both average mean were above the criterion mean of 2.5 and this implies that both male and female teachers agreed on the strategies for improving institutional safeguarding policies for minors' protection in private secondary schools in Rivers State.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female respondents on the level of training on institutional safeguarding policies for minors' protection in private Secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4.3: z-test Analysis on the Difference between the Mean Rating Scores of male and female respondents on the level of training on institutional safeguarding policies for minors' protection in private Secondary schools in Rivers State.

Category	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	Df	z-cal	z-crit.	Remarks
Male	108	2.72	0.82	253	0.088	±1.96	significant
Female	147	2.71	0.99				Not Accept Ho ₁ (z-cal. > z-crit.)
Total	255			255			

Table 4.3 uncovered that male teacher have mean and standard deviation scores of 2.72 and 0.82 while female teacher have mean and standard deviation scores of 2.71 and 0.99 respectively. With a level of flexibility of 255 at an alpha noteworthy level of 0.05; the figured z-estimation of 0.088 is higher than the z-critical of -1.96. Along these lines the null hypothesis is rejected. By implication, there is a significant difference in the mean scores of male and female respondents on the level of training on institutional safeguarding policies for minors' protection in private Secondary schools in Rivers State.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female respondents on the strategies for improving institutional safeguarding policies for minors' protection in private Secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4.4: z-test Analysis on the Difference between the Mean Rating Scores of male and female respondents on the strategies for improving institutional safeguarding policies for minors' protection in private Secondary schools in Rivers State.

Category	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	Df	z-cal	z-crit.	Remarks
Male	108	2.69	0.83	253	1.41	±1.96	significant
Female	147	2.54	0.85				not Accept Ho ₆ (z-cal. < z-crit.)
Total	255			255			

Table 4.4 uncovered that male teachers have mean and standard deviation scores of 2.69 and 0.82 while female teachers have mean and standard deviation scores of 2.54 and 0.85 respectively. With a level of flexibility of 253 at an alpha noteworthy level of 0.05; the figured z-estimation of 1.41 is greater than the z-critical of -1.96. Along these lines the null hypothesis is rejected. By implication, there is significant difference in the mean scores of male and female respondents on the strategies for improving institutional safeguarding policies for minors' protection in private Secondary schools in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Institutional safeguarding policies for minors' protection availability

The study examined the safeguarding policies for protecting minors in private secondary schools in Rivers State. According to the respondents, the school has specific safeguarding policies that are approved and signed off by the principal and director of Diocesan Education Board. These policies are readily available on the school's intranet and internet sites, visible and accessible within the school premises, and reviewed every three years or when changes occur in the school or legislative. The study also found a significant difference in the level of training on institutional safeguarding policies for minors' protection between male and female respondents. Safeguarding, as defined by Avert (2019), involves taking reasonable steps to prevent harm, particularly sexual exploitation, abuse, and harassment, and responding appropriately when harm occurs. It encompasses ensuring the safety and welfare of vulnerable adults and children who are beneficiaries of institutional services. This aligns with the views of ROSPA (2019) and Stoke Primary School (2019), which emphasize the responsibility of schools to establish a safe teaching and learning environment for students and staff, taking into consideration the impact of their activities on all individuals involved.

Strategies in place for improving institutional safeguarding policies for Minors' protection

The study findings discussed the various strategies for improving institutional safeguarding policies for the protection of minors. The respondents emphasized the importance of having designated staff to oversee the implementation of safeguarding policies, conducting annual self-audit for safeguarding practices, providing new staff with copies of safeguarding policies and a code of conduct, and ensuring that staff are aware of and agree to act in accordance with the policies. Additionally, the study highlighted the need for providing appropriate care, support, and protection to staff/students who report child safeguarding concerns or are accused of abuse. It also emphasized the significance of maintaining confidentiality during the investigation of allegations to protect the child and manage related disciplinary processes. Furthermore, the study noted that it is important to treat records of minor's protection concern disclosure or allegation as sensitive information and to share the information only with those who need to have it to safeguard the students or carry out their duties. The study also noted a significant difference in the mean scores of male and female respondents on the strategies for improving institutional safeguarding policies. These findings align with established safeguarding procedures and emphasize the importance of confidentiality and appropriate handling of information related to safeguarding concerns.

CONCLUSION

Based on the comprehensive findings of the study, along with the in-depth discussions surrounding them and their profound educational implications, it is deduced that the appropriate implementation of institutional safeguarding policies among private schools in Rivers State carries significant importance. These policies encompass aspects such as availability, effectiveness, the level of training for staff, volunteers, and students, compliance mechanisms, the challenges that hinder effective implementation, as well as the strategies for enhancing institutional safeguarding policies. Ultimately, these policies are pivotal in ensuring the protection of minors in private secondary schools in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of the conclusion of the study, it is recommended as follows:

1. As school administrators and other stakeholders in school administration, it is crucial to consistently implement and uphold safeguarding policies in order to create a safe and sustainable learning environment within schools.
2. All stakeholders in school administration, including principals, teachers, non-teaching personnel, students, parents, as well as other public-spirited individuals and groups, should work together to ensure that institutional safeguarding policies for the protection of minors are effectively implemented and adhered to in every educational institution. This collective effort is essential for creating a safe and secure environment where the well-being of all students is prioritized.

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